

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF SOIL BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY IN LABORATORY CONDITIONS (IN THE MODIFIED FORM OF G.A. OGANOV'S METHODOLOGY)

Guliyeva R.

Head teacher

Huseynzade E.

Head teacher

Azerbaijan State Agrarian University

Ganja

ABSTRACT

Object of study: Shekinsky district of the Azerbaijan Republic, agricultural enterprise "Garatorpag" sowing of agricultural crops was carried out by strip method, alternating sowing with steam.

Research results: soil samples were taken from the depth of 0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, 20-30 cm. Biological activity was determined by releasing CO₂ and binding to 0.1 N NaOH. Incubation in a thermostat was carried out for 5-6 hours at a temperature of 28-29 °C. The amount of released CO₂ was determined by titration with 0.1 N HCl. It is established that the biological activity on the strips under steam at a depth of 0-10 cm is lower than on the sowing strips. However, at a depth of 10-20 cm, the biological activity on the strips under steam turned out to be somewhat higher than on the sown strips.

Keywords: biological activity, fertility, microorganism, soil.

Biological activity in soil is produced by living organisms living in soil. They participate in the carbon cycle, a global process. During photosynthesis, plants absorb CO₂ from the air and enrich the atmosphere with oxygen. The carbon cycle in the soil is the most basic geochemical cycle on the planet, which keeps the carbon-oxygen system of the earth stable. In the carbon cycle, there are two areas on a planetary scale, which are the creation and assimilation of oxygen: 1. CO₂ fixation and generation of oxygen in the process of photosynthesis; 2. Excretion of CO₂ and consumption of oxygen as a result of mineralization of organic matter. The first process is mainly carried out by plants, and the second by microorganisms.

A primary organic product is formed from carbon dioxide. Its amount in the atmosphere is up to 0.03%, and it is much more in the soil air. The biological use of carbon is carried out in photosynthesis, hemosynthesis and heterotrophic fixation. The photosynthesis process takes place mainly in the upper soil layer of the biosphere, while the hemosynthesis and heterotrophic processes take place in the soil.

The main indicator of the biological activity of the soil is the release rate of gaseous carbon dioxide, which also characterizes the "breathing" property of the soil during ecological monitoring of the soil and allows for a comprehensive assessment of the condition of the soil together with the results of studies conducted by classical morphological methods and chemical analysis.

Based on the above, it becomes clear how important it is to study the biological activity of the soil and how important this indicator is.

Recently, many researchers have used soil biological activity as a basis for assessing soil fertility by studying the intensity of CO₂ released from the soil. The development of the methodology for determining biological activity is associated with the name of V. I. Shtatnov (1952). In the methodology proposed by him, biological activity is determined under field conditions.

At this time, a certain area of the soil is covered with a cylindrical container and the CO₂ released from the soil is combined with a weak alkaline solution (NaOH, Ba(OH)₂). In laboratory conditions, the author suggests that a certain amount of soil be kept indoors and a weak solution of NaOH or Ba(OH)₂ colored with 1% phenolphthalein be added to it. After 2-3 hours, the alkali is titrated with weak (0.1 N) HCl acid and the amount of CO₂ is determined by calculation. Although Oganov's methodology is quite simple, mistakes can be made during its application. Once the soil sample and alkali are placed in a closed container to obtain an accurate result, it is impossible to shake the alkali, resulting in an under-indication of CO₂. In addition, difficulties arise in using a thermostat for initial incubation during mass analyses.

Taking these into account, we have made several changes to this methodology. In order to determine the biological activity of the soil, we took 2 conical flasks for each sample with a volume of 500 ml. The neck of these flasks should be wide so that the screw attached to the stopper can be easily inserted into the flask. A specially shaped bracket should be connected to the inner side of the plug so that a 25 ml bottle can be placed here. A glass tube should be made according to the size of the box. Washed and burned sand should be poured into the bottom of the box - the place where the pipe is placed, approximately 0.3-0.4g. The purpose of pouring sand is to ensure that the water added to the glass tube is gradually absorbed into the soil through drainage.

20 g of air-dried soil sample passed through a 1-2 mm sieve is taken inside the boxes.

Before starting the analysis, the amount of total water in the soil sample that entered the laboratory should be determined. For this purpose, approximately 5 g of soil with initial moisture content is taken in a

porcelain bowl or Petri dish and dried in a drying cabinet at 105°C for 5-6 hours. The total water in the soil is calculated as follows:

$$N = \frac{a - b}{b - q} \cdot 100$$

Here, N-total moisture; a – weight of the bag with wet soil; b – the weight of the soil after drying for 5 hours; q – empty weight of the package.

Along with these operations, hygroscopic water should also be determined in the same soil sample that has been dried in the air and passed through a 0.25 mm sieve.

Before placing the soil sample in the thermostat for incubation, the amount of water added to bring the soil to initial moisture should be calculated as follows. For example: Let's say that the total water content at the first moisture was 23%, and the hygroscopic moisture was 4%. The amount of water to be added should be calculated as follows: if 100g of soil contains 23g of water, 20g of soil contains 4.6g of water. A hygroscopic moisture content of 4% means that 20g of soil contains 0.8g of hygroscopic water. So, if we subtract the hygroscopic water from the total water (4.6g-0.8g=3.8g), then 3.8g of water should be added to the soil sample. This amount of water restores the life activity of soil organisms existing there by bringing the soil sample to the first moisture. During the incubation period (5-6 hours), the temperature of the thermostat should be 27-28°C to create optimal conditions for the activity of living things in the soil. The incubation period depends on the amount of organic matter in the soil.

The biological activity of the soil is measured by the amount of CO₂ formed during the incubation period. 25 ml of 0.1N NaOH (or 0.1N KOH) and 1-2 drops of 1% phenolphthalein solution are added to the bottom of the flask to keep the separated CO₂ in the solution. When adding phenolphthalein, the solution acquires a faint pink color. After the end of incubation, 1-2 ml of 20% BaCl₂ solution is added to 0.1N NaOH. Oganov recommends adding 2 drops of 50% BaCl₂ to the solution in the flask before incubation. In our opinion, 1 drop of BaCl₂ is enough for such addition and this addition should be done after incubation, because the effect of BaCl₂ can be negative in the reaction. The purpose of doing this is to precipitate sulfate ions if they happen to be in the soil. Next, the solution at the bottom of the flask is titrated with 0.1 n HCl. All operations performed on the soil sample should be performed in the same manner on the control sample without soil. Because water, air, jets also contain CO₂. The flask should be gently shaken several times during incuba-

tion. It would be better to open the door of the thermostat every hour and do this without leaving the thermostat.

The titration consumption of 0.1 n HCl to the control solution exceeds that of the sample. That difference should be multiplied by 2.2 mg. 2.2 mg of CO₂ corresponds to 1 ml of alkali. By multiplying the obtained result by 50 (or by multiplying by 1000 and dividing by 20), we find the difference spent on titration and sample to convert 1 kg of soil. For example: Let's say that 18.2 ml of 0.1 N HCl was used for the titration of NaOH in the control flask, and 16.3 ml was used in the sample. The difference is 1.9 ml (18.2-16.3). Multiply 1.9 ml by 2.2 mg of CO₂ and get 4.18 mg per 20 g of soil. To find the amount of CO₂ released from 1 kg of soil, 4.18·1000/20=209mg is taken.

When determining biological activity in the soil, CO₂ gas is formed, which participates in the following reaction:

1-2ml of 20% BaCl₂ solution is added to 0.1N NaOH to precipitate SO₄⁺⁺ ions in the soil, the reaction goes like this:

2.

The following formula is used to determine biological activity in 1 kg of absolute dry soil:

$$V_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{(a - b) \cdot K \cdot 1000}{C} K_h,$$

Here, V_{CO₂}- the volume of carbon dioxide in the soil; 0.1N HCl used for the titration of a-control, in ml; b- 0.1N HCl used for titration of the sample, in ml; K- 0.1N NaOH, in ml, corresponding to mg of CO₂ (2.2 mg); C- mass of air-dried soil sample, 20g; K_h- coefficient of conversion of each sample to absolute dry soil;

In order to study the biological activity in the soil, in the experiment conducted at the "Ganja Regional Agrarian Science and Innovation Center of the Ministry of Agriculture" located in the Samukh region, we conventionally collected 6 fields (lanes) from 3 depths (0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm). we took a soil sample. From the 18 soil samples included in the laboratory, the total moisture content was determined first, and then the soil samples were dried in the open air for 4-5 days. Hygroscopic moisture was determined in air-dried soil samples after passing through a 0.25 mm sieve. The obtained results were used to determine the biological activity of the soil. The indicators of biological activity of 18 soil samples are reflected in table No. 1. From the obtained results, it is clear that the biological activity varies at different depths, and this difference is also evident between the strips.

Table 1

Average indicators of biological activity, CO₂ mg/kg in soil samples brought from the Ganja Regional Agrarian Science and Innovation Center of the Ministry of Agriculture located in Samukh district

Field condition	Depth in cm	Sample number	Coefficient of conversion to absolute dry soil, K _h	Biological activity, CO ₂ mg/kg in absolute dry soil
Empty	0-10	1 ₁	1.08	184.14
	10-20	1 ₂	1.0825	232.2
	20-30	1 ₃	1.08	178.2
Sprinkle	0-10	2 ₁	1.086	304.62
	10-20	2 ₂	1.0876	197.4
	20-30	2 ₃	1.0817	196.33
Empty	0-10	3 ₁	1.0791	261.14
	10-20	3 ₂	1.0772	296.23
	20-30	3 ₃	1.0835	220.49
Sprinkle	0-10	4 ₁	1.0833	297.91
	10-20	4 ₂	1.0773	219.23
	20-30	4 ₃	1.0797	201.90
Empty	0-10	5 ₁	1.0832	285.96
	10-20	5 ₂	1.0899	317.70
	20-30	5 ₃	1.0861	232.97
Sprinkle	0-10	6 ₁	1.0786	266.95
	10-20	6 ₂	1.0784	255.04
	20-30	6 ₃	1.0830	177.46

Chart 1

The results obtained during the experiment were processed by mathematical calculations according to the general rule:

$$M = \frac{\sum n}{n}$$

Here: M-average; Σ - sum of obtained results; n- number of analyses;

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum a^2}{n-1}}$$

σ -mean square deviation; a- deviation from average indicators;

$$m = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} ; m\text{-average error;}$$

$$P = \frac{m \cdot 100\%}{M}; \text{ P-accuracy index (4)}$$

Mathematical calculations made it possible to clearly show the difference between the indicators of biological activity of empty (rested) and sowing areas. From the indicators in graph No. 1 and table No. 2, it is clear that there is indeed a difference between empty and seeded areas at the same depth. Thus, the biological activity in the empty fields, in the upper layer, was less than in the seeded fields. This shows that microorganisms are more active in the top layer of the sowing area.

Therefore, biological activity is higher in sowing areas than in rest areas. This comparison is also reflected in other examples. Thus, a sharp difference was observed in the upper layers. It can be seen from the table that in sample 1, the biological activity was 190.08 in the rest areas and 250.87 in the sowing areas, the difference is 6.79 or 31.98%. In sample 2, the biological activity was 249.27 in the rest areas and 266.13 in the sowing areas, the difference is 16.86 or 6.76%. In the 3rd sample, the biological activity was 254.19 in the rest areas and 264.98 in the sowing areas, the difference is 10.79 or 4.24%. Biological activity has weakened in the lower layers. It is clear from the table that slight differences were observed in the lower layers.

Table 2

Biological activity values in absolute dry soil comparatively, n=3

Sample number	Empty	Degree of accuracy, P	Sample number	Sprinkle	Degree of accuracy, P
	M±m			M±m	
1 ₁	190.08±9.70	5.10	2 ₁	250.87±13.79	5.50
1 ₂	250.06±21.19	8.47	2 ₂	195.41±3.98	2.04
1 ₃	182.16±10.48	5.75	2 ₃	202.28±11.90	5.88
3 ₁	249.27±11.87	4.76	4 ₁	266.13±10.51	3.95
3 ₂	264.63±3.30	1.25	4 ₂	217.25±10.45	4.81
3 ₃	218.50±10.51	4.81	4 ₃	209.82±7.92	3.77
5 ₁	254.19±3.97	1.55	6 ₁	264.98±10.38	3.92
5 ₂	275.74±6.92	2.51	6 ₂	209.57±10.46	4.99
5 ₃	230.98±7.96	3.45	6 ₃	298.55±10.51	5.29

The result

1. Biological activity is different in a rested strip compared to a sprayed strip, regardless of depth.
2. In the soil samples taken from 0-10 cm depth, the biological activity is higher in the sown strips.
3. Biological activity is weak in both lanes (D and S) at 20-30 cm depth, because the life activity of microorganisms has weakened when sampling here.
4. The high level of biological activity (298.55±10.51 mg/kg CO₂) at the depth of 20-30 cm in strip No. 6, where sowing was carried out, indicates that wheat seeds accidentally fell to this depth.

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